

COVID-19: A makeover among student teachers to be the 'new normal'

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Abstract

In the higher education sector, the Covid-19 epidemic has posed problems and caused interferences. University campuses and institutions were shut down, and face-to-face instruction and evaluation moved to an online environment. The obstacles brought on by the pandemic in the day-to-day activities of teaching and learning persisted even in teacher education. We will be able to better shape future hybrid delivery by using the experiences of the student instructors during this time to make it best fit the teaching and learning process in the future. The study looked at the experiences of the student teachers who were learning from home as well as how the lockout affected their quality of life and mental health. In an online survey with both open-ended and closed-ended questions, 200 student instructors participated. The data analysis showed that most student teachers had positive experiences with online learning and assessments, social media use, environmentally friendly practices, online shopping, dietary practices, and the use of electronic devices for health and fitness, and most of them wished to continue these practices in the future. The majority of students reported having no technical problems and having decent internet connectivity. While seeking more interactive lectures, only half of the students felt comfortable interacting with video cameras, which was shown when the focus shifted to the continuous hours of online sessions. Open-ended comments gave us a glimpse into how some students felt their home workspaces were insufficient, that using ICT was unhealthy, that it affected their concentration, that it made it hard to sleep, and that their mental health had declined.

KeyWords: Covid-19 pandemic, Teacher Education, Challenges, Lockdown, Online learning

Introduction

The pandemic has created substantial difficulties in the routine tasks of education. Lockdowns and the forced closure of schools, colleges, and universities during the past year have been the direct effects. However, this has not resulted in a stop to learning, teaching, or assessment; rather, online platforms were created to carry on teaching and evaluation through a digital interface so students can advance in their academic careers. Many universities had already developed procedures to adapt their methods of delivering education to student requirements. However, all students must participate in both modalities. While blended learning incorporates some components of course delivery online, other strategies use the hybrid model, which combines online course delivery with in-person meetings. It has undoubtedly been difficult for academics and students alike to deal with the first global pandemic to affect higher education institutions in recent memory. To better prepare for future disruptions to higher education levels and to comprehend how COVID-19 has shaped our students, it is crucial to learn about student teachers' experiences during this time. This is especially true given that research has shown that COVID-19 has a significant negative impact on the general public's mental health and wellbeing. It has undoubtedly been difficult for academics and students alike to deal with the first global pandemic to affect higher education institutions in recent memory. To better prepare for future disruptions to

higher education levels and to comprehend how COVID-19 has shaped our students, it is crucial to learn about student teachers' experiences during this time. This is especially true given that research has shown that COVID-19 has a significant negative impact on the general public's mental health and wellbeing. The student teachers underwent noticeable change as a result of college closures, the rise of digital education, and time spent at home. The student teachers underwent noticeable change as a result of college closures, the rise of digital education, and time spent at home. As a result the effect of pandemic reflected upon every aspects of life. These pandemic induced habits among student teachers are observable when they set back to the normal life. As a teacher educator it has been observed that there is a drastic change in the behaviour and lifestyle of student teachers. While interacting with them it was realised that their attitude towards life, their hobbies, learning style, approach towards nature and society, practical knowledge regarding the use of electronic gadgets everything was undergone a rapid change. So it is very important to study about the impact of pandemic on various habits among student teachers

Research questions

The present study was designed to answer the following research questions.

1. Does the pandemic induce any change in the habits and life styles of student teachers?
2. Whether all the pandemic induced aspects are to be sustained for the future?

Objectives of the study

The major objectives of the present study are;

1. To study about the major pandemic induced habits among student teachers
2. To analyze the extent to which the pandemic influenced on aspects like the pattern of using of social media, learning habits, online shopping, eco-friendly habits, outlook towards nature, dietary habits ,health & fitness and usage of different gadgets
3. To analyze the major challenges faced in online learning by the student teachers
4. To look over, the reaction of the student teachers whether the pandemic induced aspects are to be sustained for the future.

Hypothesis of the study

1. COVID-19 pandemic has induced several habitual changes among student teachers

Methodology in brief

In this study, the investigator adopted normative survey method to collect the data required. In order to collect the data required to study the pandemic induced habits among the student teachers, a

questionnaire was prepared by the investigator. It includes both open ended and closed ended questions. The questionnaire in Google form was shared on whatsapp and the responses were collected .The sample for the present study consists of 200 student teachers from three teacher education institutions in Kollam district. Computation of percentages was done to decide the proportion of responses made by the subjects under study

Analysis and Interpretation of the data

Analysis and interpretation of data regarding the pandemic induced habits among student teachers were done under the following sections.

I) Analysis with respect to the various pandemic induced habits identified among student teachers

a) Usage of social media

The student teachers of the present day are living in a knowledge driven era. They use many social platforms for various purposes without any age barriers. In this section the responses of the student teachers regarding usage of social media after COVID-19 pandemic were analyzed and interpreted as below.

Table 1(a):Extent of usage of social media after COVID-19pandemic among student teachers

Extent of use of social media	Number of student teachers	Percentage (%)
Great extent	183	91.6%
Some extent	17	8.4%
Not a tall	0	0%

Among the 200 student teachers selected for the study183(91.6%)students responded that the extent of social media usage rate increased due to the digital rush aroused during and after corona

pandemic. The table 1(b) describes the responses of student teachers with respect to the various purposes of using social media.

Table 1 (b): Responses of student teachers with regard to the various purposes of using social media.

Responses of using social media	Number of student teachers	Percentage (%)
Learning	67	33.3%
Entertainment	90	45%
Communication	13	6.7%
Others	30	15%

The table 1(b), reveals that 67 (45%) student teachers used social media for the purpose of entertainment. About 90 (33.3%) student teachers used social media for the purpose of learning and 13 (6.7%) using various social platforms for communication. From this it can be concluded that, they may have developed the habit of use of social media mainly for entertainment and learning due to non-functioning of the college.

b) Learning habits

The pandemic influenced student teachers' life a lot. Closure of colleges and shifting the learning into online platform affected the learning pattern of student teachers. In this section the responses of student teachers towards their learning habits were analyzed and the data was interpreted as given below.

Table2: Responses of student teachers with respect to their learning habits

Learning habits	Number of student teachers	Percentage (%)
Learning by using different gadgets	57	28.3%
Reading habit	33	16.7%
Self-learning	50	25%
Learning by discovering facts	20	10%

Others	40	20%
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From the table 2, it is revealed that among the sample collected 57(28.3%) student teachers carry out learning by using different gadgets. The learning and teaching through Google meet may have helped them in continuing the course. This means about 50(25%) student teachers developed a habit towards self-learning by exploring different information rich platforms available on internet. There were only about 33(16.7%) student teachers developed a habit of learning through reading. Also, the tendency of

discovery learning developed only in 20 (10%) student teachers. From this, it can be concluded that they may have developed a new habit of learning due to the spread of COVID -19 pandemic.

c. Online shopping

COVID-19 pandemic made people to be digital in all aspects. In this section the responses of student teachers on their habit of online shopping were analyzed and the data was interpreted as given below.

Table3: Responses of student teachers with regard to online shopping

Online shopping	Number of student teachers	Percentage(%)
YES	113	56.7%
NO	87	43.3%

The table 3 reveals that among the sample studied 113 (56.7%) student teachers carry out online shopping whereas only 87(43.3%) student teachers not use any means for online shopping. From this, it can be concluded that pandemic may have developed a habit of online shopping by using various digital platforms due to COVID-19 pandemic.

d) Eco friendly Habit

The COVID-19 pandemic set back people towards nature. The table 4 shows the development of various eco-friendly approaches of student teachers and the eco-friendly habits developed in them.

Table 4: Development of eco-friendly habits among student teachers

Eco-friendly habits	Number of student teachers	Percentage (%)
Gardening	39	19.5%
Aspects of conservation	20	10%
Observing nature	20	10%
Aspects of cleanliness	27	13.5%
Pet rearing	44	22%
Farming	50	25%

The table 4 indicates that the student teachers have done different activities to enjoy their leisure time as well as the students got more attached with nature during the period of pandemic. From the responses of the student teachers most of them have developed habits like farming 50(25%), pet rearing 44 (22%) and gardening 39 (19.5%)From this, it can be concluded that the student teachers may have

developed a habit of getting attached with the Mother Nature more than before.

e. Dietary habits

In this section the responses of student teachers on their dietary habits were analyzed and the data was interpreted as given below. The table 5 describes the responses of student teachers with respect to their dietary intake during COVID-19

Table 5: Responses of student teachers with respect to their change in dietary intake during COVID-19

Dietary habits	Number of student teachers	Percentage(%)
YES	153	76.7%
NO	13	6.6%
No change	34	16.7%

From the table 5, it is revealed that among the responses collected, 153(76.7%) student teachers had changed their dietary habits by getting back to natural food resources available in our surroundings.

They started to follow a new diet containing natural food items like jackfruit, papaya, elephant yam etc., which is available in our surroundings.

f) Health and fitness

Where only 13(6.6%) student teachers responded that they had no interest in the natural dietary resources. And 34 (16.7%) opined that pandemic did not change their diet. From this, it can be concluded that the student teachers may have developed a new

During the COVID-19 pandemic the people became more conscious about their health and fitness.COVID-19 pandemic has become a cause for maintaining good health. In this section the responses of student teachers on their habits

developed with regard to health and fitness were analyzed and the data was interpreted as given below.

Table 6: Responses of student teachers with respect to the habit of developing health and fitness.

Health and fitness	Number of student teachers	Percentage(%)
Exercising daily	67	33.4%
Reduced use of junk food	40	20%
Included nutrient rich food supplements in diet	60	30%
others	33	16.6%

From the Table 6, it is revealed that among the responses, 67(33.4%) student teachers exercise daily. About 60(30%) student teachers started to follow nutrient rich diet and 40(20%) student teachers reduced the use of junk food. From this, it can be concluded that pandemic may have developed a positive habit towards health and fitness.

g) Use of different gadgets

Pandemic has directed people to the use of many gadgets like mobile phone, PCs, laptops, Tablets etc. for exploring the digital world. The technological competencies were changed. COVID-19 pandemic also developed a habit of being digital in many aspects. In this section the responses of secondary school students on their habit and competencies of use of various gadgets were analyzed and the data was interpreted as given below.

Table7: Responses of student teachers with regard to the habit of using various electronic gadgets

Use of electronic gadgets	Number of student teachers	Percentage(%)
YES	180	90%
NO	20	10%

From the table7, it is revealed that among the sample collected 180(90%) student teachers have developed a technical skill in the use of various electronic gadgets. Only 20(10%) student teachers have given negative responses with regard to the competencies developed for using gadgets. From this, it can be concluded that pandemic may have increased the use of different gadgets.

h) Challenges reported by student teachers during online learning-Thematic analysis

What were the main difficulties that student teachers had with online learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic? A thematic analysis of the responses was done. Is there anything that could be done to enhance the way that learning and teaching happens online? The free-text questions and responses were chosen by the student teachers. Following are the major themes. While seeking more interactive lectures, only half of the students felt comfortable interacting with video cameras, which was shown when the focus shifted to the continuous hours of online sessions. Open ended responses revealed how several students felt their home workspaces were insufficient and that utilising ICT poses health risks. The constant usage of ICT equipment caused various health problems among the student instructors. Headaches, neck discomfort, watery eyes, joint pain, decreased concentration, trouble sleeping, back pain, and a decline in mental wellbeing are among the main health risks mentioned by the student instructors. They also

reported headaches, neck pain, difficulty sleeping, and back pain.

II) Analysis with respect to the pandemic induced aspects that are to be sustained for the future.

From the open ended responses of the student teachers, the following suggestions were developed with respect to the pandemic induced aspects that are to be sustained for the future.

1. The learning through online platforms influenced the student teachers and it is good to sustain the habit of online learning/teaching or developing a style of education in which students learn via electronic and online media as well as traditional face to face teaching. In short, the student teachers prefer greatly for a blended mode of learning.
2. Due to the influence of pandemic , the student teachers have developed a Habit of getting attached with the Mother Nature more than before. This should be sustained for the future. By developing an eco-friendly attitude, the student teachers get more involved in nurturing and conserving nature and natural resources moving towards the concept of sustainable development.
3. From the opinion of the student teachers the adoption of new dietary habits during the time of pandemic should be sustained for future. Because it reduces the use
4. of junk foods and people started to use the items available in their locality, like raw papaya, jack fruit, tapioca, elephant yam etc. it is good for

health and this food habits should be sustained for future.

5. COVID-19 pandemic has become a cause for maintaining good health. Pandemic has developed a positive habit towards health and fitness like daily exercise, reduced use of junk foods, including nutrient rich food supplements in diet etc and these habits should be sustained for better future.

Conclusion

The pandemic has demonstrated how flexible academics and students are in the higher education environment, allowing for the continuation of online study and evaluation.. Corona virus disease affected all type of individuals and their life style; it influenced the student teachers and their living pattern. Institutional life provides structure and routine to the lives of students. But, closure of colleges and emergence of digital education and the time spent at home made an observable changes among student teachers. As a result the effect of pandemic induced several changes in their habits. Also, it developed new habits among student teachers in various aspects like Usage of social media, Online shopping, Eco-friendly habits, Dietary habits, Health and fitness, Usage of different gadgets, Interest in sports, Interest in arts, Sleeping habits etc. These pandemic induced habits among student teachers are observable when they set back to the normal life and some pandemic induced habits have a positive impact on life and these aspects are to be sustained for the future touching student wellbeing.

Students are better equipped to work remotely thanks to the pandemic, which is a necessary component of offering a successful hybrid model and represents the widespread adjustments made by many organisations to respond to changing laws, regulations, and guidelines. There are undeniable benefits to online education, as well as potential for colleges to gain from rising social media usage. However, our study has clearly revealed a problem of online learning: making sure our students feel at ease interacting and participating online. Universities might utilize video cameras to duplicate classroom interactions online, but teachers need to be aware of how much privacy their students demand. The use of a hybrid teaching, learning, and evaluation strategy must be encouraged by educational institutions, who must also embrace the lessons acquired through online instruction.

Bibliography

1. Bao, W. (2020). COVID-19 and online teaching in higher education: A case study of Peking University. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies*, 2(2), 113-115.
2. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.191>

3. Dhawan, S. (2020). Online Learning: A Panacea in the Time of COVID-19 Crisis. *J. Educ. Tech. Syst.* 49 (1), 5–22. doi:10.1177/0047239520934018
4. Hall, S., and Villareal, D. (2015). The Hybrid Advantage: Graduate Student
5. Perspectives of Hybrid Education Courses. *Int. J. Teach. Learn. Higher Edu.* 27 (1), 69–80.
6. Ingram, J., Maciejewski, G., and Hand, C. J. (2020). Changes in Diet, Sleep, and Physical Activity Are Associated with Differences in Negative Mood during COVID-19 Lockdown. *Front. Psychol.* 11, 588604. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2020.588604
7. Malcolm, D., and Velija, P. (2020). COVID-19, Exercise and Bodily Self-Control. *Sd 1* (1), 29–34. doi:10.46661/socioldeporte.5011
8. Rapanta, C., Botturi, L., Goodyear, P., Guàrdia, L., and Koole, M. (2020). Online University Teaching during and after the Covid-19 Crisis: Refocusing Teacher Presence and Learning Activity. *Postdigit Sci. Educ.* 2, 923–945. doi:10.1007/s42438-020-00155-y
9. Shin, M., and Hickey, K. (2020). Needs a Little TLC: Examining College Students'
10. Emergency Remote Teaching and Learning Experiences during COVID-19. *J. Further Higher Edu.*, 1–14. doi:10.1080/0309877X.2020.1847261
11. Watermeyer, R., Crick, T., Knight, C., and Goodall, J. (2020). COVID-19 and Digital Disruption in UK Universities: Afflictions and Affordances of Emergency Online Migration. *High Educ.* 81, 623–641. doi:10.1007/s10734-020-00561-y
12. White, R. G., and Van Der Boor, C. (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic and Initial Period of Lockdown on the Mental Health and Well-Being of Adult in the UK. *BJPsych open* 6 (5), E90. doi:10.1192/bjo.2020.79